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MONITORING OF ATTENDANCE USING RFID AND GSM TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract:

In recent years, the number of applications based on Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) systems have been rise, and they have been successfully applied to different areas such as transportation, health-care, agriculture, hospitality, industry, and schools. RFID technology facilitates the automatic wireless identification using electronic passive and active tags with suitable readers. Monitoring of students has become more important part of any institution / organization. This paper represents the automatic computing system in classrooms for managing student's attendance using RFID. RFID is used to solve problems where it is necessary to automatically record the student's attendance in classrooms. To communicate wirelessly with a reader in order to identify the students, the RFID tag is affixed on identity card. RFID is an automated identification and data collection technology, that ensures more accurate and timely data entry. RFID combines radio frequency and microchip technologies to create a smart system GSM is used to provide communication between administrative of the institutions and the parents by sending message regarding students attendance report.

Keywords- Lecture, Attendance, passive tag, RFID Reader, etc

I. Introduction

In a classroom the individuals gather for the purpose of learning and studying. The classroom may be of a primary school, an elementary school, a college or a university - but the purpose remains the same. A classroom should be made like a place where students get the compulsion to grow and develop themselves professionally and mentally. But until now, class attendance records have been maintained manually by calling students roll no. during class. This method is out-dated, time-consuming and a distraction for both student and professor. The application of RFID Technology to student monitoring problem especially in developing countries will lead to reduction of the quality time wasted during manual collection of attendance [5].

Creation of a student database management system that is not liable to errors.

Student's monitoring system deals with maintenance of student's attendance automatically using RFID. By using radio waves, the system transmits the identity of a student wirelessly. RFID is an automated identification and data collection technology, that ensures more accurate and timely data entry. RFID combines radio frequency and microchip technologies to create a smart system. This system can be used to identify, monitor, secure and do object inventory. RFID system use tiny chips called —tags that transmit some piece of identifying information to an RFID reader [1]. A RFID tag is attached to an object like id card and it is given to every student and professor.

GSM is used to provide communication between administrative of the institutions and the parents by sending message regarding students attendance report. A GSM modem is a wireless modem that works with a GSM wireless network. GSM modem sends and receive the data through the radio waves. GSM was designed with a moderate level of service security. The system was designed to authenticate the subscriber using a pre-shared key and challenge-response. If a particular student comes late to class continuously for three days, then all his concerned details will be sent as message to the Head of the Department and parents [9].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Barcode has been used in student identity card for attendance purpose [6]. It is a visual representation of data that is scanned and interpreted for information. At the same time, the conventional method of taking attendance in every lecturer / lab by calling names /

roll numbers or signing on paper is very time consuming, unsecured, inefficient, difficult and monotonous for faculty. Their valuable time is wasted in taking attendance. Therefore many times proper attendance is not taken by the faculty. Also proxy attendance is always a problem in most of the campuses. Government & statutory bodies are also insisting Institutions for full proof attendance system. Further compilation of attendance reports and communication with parents is further a tough activity for Institute Administration. Even if a student is missing the classes for almost 15 days, in-time communication in the existing manual attendance system without any software is difficult task. Since Institute do not have a full proof attendance automation & monitoring system, there is a tendency of missing the classes by students which affects his Academic performance seriously.

A. Barcode

Barcode technology is a method of identification which is used to retrieve in a shape of symbol generally in bar, vertical, space, square and dots which have different width with each one. A reader or scanners are needed to identify the data that are represented by each barcode by using light beam and scan directly to barcode [3]. During scanning process, a scanner measured the intensity of reflected light at black and white region. A black region will absorb the light meanwhile white region will reflected it. There are several types of code bar scanner:

- Pen Reader
- Laser Reader
- Charge Coupled Device (CCD) Reader
- Camera Reader

The existing system in the Barcode based student attendance system which would prone to few drawbacks that includes -

- Less security
- It can be easily reproduced or forged.
- If a barcode is damaged, there is no way to scan the product.
- Very limited data can be stored in barcode.

III. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF RFID SYSTEM

Figure 1: Block diagram of RFID System

This paper concentrates on the principal purpose to overcome the human errors while recording student attendance and the creation of a data centric student attendance database system with an improved overall efficiency. The application graphical user interface (GUI) is designed using Visual Basic 6.03 and Microsoft Access is used as the database provider. The Atmel4 AT89S52 is the heart of the system, which is a low-power high performance CMOS 8-bit microcomputer with 8K bytes of downloadable flash programmable and erasable read only memory. It is operable in two modes namely (1) Idle mode and (2) Power down mode [8]. The microcontroller can be programmed with the 80C51 instruction set along with additional standardised features.

The circuit contains a 16x2 LCD7 display panel, which is the output device of the system [7]. It displays the user's information when the stored tag is read by the reader. The serial interface allows connectivity to a local database for data storage and retrieval. The input to the system is the unique tag identifier stored in the RF tag, which is sensed by the reader. The components are mounted on the printed circuit board for interconnectivity between them.

IV. COMPONENTS OF RFID SYSTEM

An RFID system consists of various components that are connected to one another by a dedicated communication path (see figure 2). The individual components are integrated into the system to implement the benefits of RFID solution [14].

The list of components is as follows:

- Tag
- Antenna
- Reader
- Middleware
- Backend database

Figure 2: Components of RFID

A. Tags

An object that is attached to any product and uses a unique sequence of characters to define it. A tag consists of a microchip that stores a unique sequence identifier that is useful in identifying objects individually. The sequence is a numeric serial, which is stored in the RFID memory. The microchip includes minute circuitry and an embedded silicon chip [9]. The tag memory can be permanent or re-writable, which can be re-programmed electronically by the reader multiple times. Tags are designed specific to its applications and environment. For example, paper-thin tags are attached to books in a library management system [11]. Tags are available in various shapes and sizes (see figure 3). Tags that are initiated by the reader are known as Passive tags, whilst those that do not require external initiation are called Active tags. A Semi-Passive tag exists, which has the features of both Active and Passive tags. Tags are operable on Microwave (2.4 – 2.5 GHz), Ultra High Frequency (UHF) (860 – 1500 MHz), High Frequency (HF) (13.56 MHz) and Low Frequency (LF) (125 kHz) .

Figure 3: Types of RFID Tags

B. Antenna

It is responsible for the transmission of information between the reader and tag using radio waves. The antenna is medium through which the tag and reader communicate with each other. It antenna can activate a passive tag and transfer data by emitting wireless impulses that has electromagnetic properties.

C. Reader

A scanning device that uses the antenna to realize the tags that are in its vicinity. It transmits signals at a certain frequencies. The reader is the most fundamental part of the RFID system. It reads raw data from the tag and transmits it to the Middleware for further processing [12]. The reader attempts to interrogate the tags at varying frequencies. The reader communicates by transmitting a beam of impulses, which encapsulate commands to the tag and listens for the tag's response. The reader also contains built in anti-collision processes, which allows the reader to read multiple tags simultaneously [11]. The reader is connected to the computer for data processing via a USB cable or over a wireless connection.

D. Middleware

It is a communication interface to interpret and process data being fed by the readers into information. It takes into account all relevant ports of communication and a software application to represent this information. The middleware is an interface required to manage the flow of data from the reader and to transmit it efficiently to the backend database management systems. The middleware monitors the number of tags present in the system and extracts relevant information from the readers [14].

E. Backend Database

A repository of information, which is designed specific to the application. The database stores records of data specific to individual. The backend database primarily deals with the storage of relevant information recorded by the reader and communicated by the middleware [7]. For example, the middleware in an automated security control system will store all tag readings taken by the reader in the database. This helps create log entries for the system [10].

V. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The below flowchart describes the flow of the system. The actual works of our system starts after the login of admin and by initializing the rfid reader. When the rfid reader gets initiated they starts emitting the frequency with respective range of their own and they detect the RFID tag i.e. Identity card which we provide to the student. The rfid readers reads the tag information and fetch the information of student, as we know that every rfid tag has its own identity which acts as primary key which refers to the database details of respective student in college. With same account we can get the attendance of the class which reduces the manual efforts and errorless attendance [8].

A careful observation of the RFID tags leads one to consider the possibility of its utilization for monitoring the attendance of students in educational institutions, with the help of program driven computers. While every student given a specific RFID tag attends the lecture through entrance door, a serial number (related to each student’s matriculation number) of tag is associated with the student database entry. So every time a student uses his/her card, the entries will be entered into the database with the time stamp. Consequently, the attendance data then can be used to create many types of reports like daily attendance details, monthly, weekly and real time feedback to parents. The attendance score calculation can be automated using the collected data. After setting up the student attendance RFID system from the mode of operation represented.

Figure 4: Flow chart

The tag is activated when it passes through a radio frequency (RF) field (125 kHz in this case), which is generated by the antenna embedded within the reader box. The program checks whether the tag is valid or not. If the tag is valid, it will continue to the database program and registers the student’s attendance for the course. If the tag is invalid, the program gives a notification that the tag has not been registered to any student and requires the user to either supply a valid tag.

TAG

Figure 5: Working of RFID system

Due to the reason of cost and flexibility of implementation, this RFID attendance design application uses a passive tag and thus for every class, students would have to bring their tags close to the reader (about 10 cm from the reader). On doing this, the reader reads the tag and the application program records the student's arrival time and when leaving the class, students will also have to bring their tags close to the reader again. With records of arrival and exit time, appropriate short message service is forwarded to the parents' mobile phone number in real time or as a weekly sms/email digest through the SMS/EMAIL gateway .

Each course lecturer has RFID tag that serves as the control for the beginning and end of classroom lecture with additional time delay for end of class activation to allow every student to record exit time on the reader. The lecturer/instructor can call for information over any student by using queries provided by the application. More flexibility and unconscious interaction of students to the developed system can be achieved by using active tags. This will increase the overall cost of the system [14].

At the end of the semester, the lecturer can grade students attendance scores in a particular course based on some specific metrics provided in the application. The selected metrics could be frequency of presence in class, duration of stay in class, punctuality, etc. The program gives the following output: student name, Matriculation number, tag ID number, department, the course in question and the attendance status based on the specified metrics. A privileged user can de-assign students from their specific tag, and reassign the tag to other students if need be as shown in the Graphical User Interfaces (GUI's) of the RFID system application control

program. The system checks the absentees and sends the message to the parents, class admin using the GSM modem. The parents are alerted that their son/daughter is absent for the selected class and the class admin will mark the absentees on the attendance sheet. This system can be implemented at each and

every gate of the college so that we can know the status of the student.

VI. GSM TECHNOLOGY

One of the most important conclusions from the early tests of the new GSM technology was that the new standard should employ Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) technology. The digital nature of GSM allows the transmission of data (both synchronous and asynchronous) to or from ISDN terminals, although the most basic service support by GSM is telephony. A GSM modem is a wireless modem that works with a GSM wireless network. GSM mode sends and receive the data through the radio waves [2].

Figure 6: GSM Modem

The GSM modem requires a SIM from the wireless carrier in order to operate. The GSM modem is connected to the microcontroller using UART and is operated by the AT commands sent from the microcontroller to the modem. A unique feature of GSM is the Short Message Service (SMS), which has achieved wide popularity as what some have called the unexpected killer application of GSM. SMS is a

bi-directional service for sending short alphanumeric message in a store-and-forward process. SMS can be used both point-to-point as well as in cell-broadcast mode. These GSM is used sending a SMS as for absentees students with parents mobile nos. The data base is already stored in the PC. Student is regularly absent with in four day or six days free voice call to call the parents mobile no.s by using GSM technology.

It uses the highly popular SIM300 module for all its operations. It comes with a standard RS232 interface which can be used to easily interface the modem to micro controllers and computers. The modem consists of all the required external circuitry required to start experimenting with the SIM300 module like the power regulation, external antenna, SIMHolder, etc. It uses the highly popular SIM300 module for all its operations. It comes with a standard RS232 interface which can be used to easily interface the modem to micro controllers and computers. The modem consists of all the required external circuitry required to start experimenting with the SIM300 module like the power regulation, external antenna, SIMHolder, etc.

VII. ADVANTAGES

- RFID technology permits no line of sight reading.
- Robustness and reliability under difficult environmental conditions.
- These tags can be read through water, snow, concrete, bricks, plastics, wood, and most non-metallic materials.
- Available in a wide variety of physical forms, shapes, sizes and protective housings.
- RFID tags can be read at very high speeds.
- The tag need not be on the surface of the object (and is therefore not subject to wear).
- The read time is typically less than 100 milliseconds.
- Large numbers of tags can be read at once rather than item by item.

VIII. APPLICATION

The primary aim of the research is to uniquely identify individual students based on their unique tag identifiers. The research should shower light on how scalable and efficient the system is . A systematic and serialized approach is required to solve this

conundrum. The key characteristics of the application include:

- Perform automated attendance
- Generate report of attendees for a particular course
- Error free tag identifier detection
- Easy scalability to incorporate more records
- Integrity and security in data storage

This paper concentrates on the principal purpose to overcome the human errors while recording student attendance and the creation of a data centric student attendance database system with an improved overall Efficiency. The input to the system is the unique tag identifier stored in the RF tag, which is sensed by the reader. The components are mounted on the printed circuit board for interconnectivity between them [4].

IX. FUTURE SCOPE

Some further improvements can be made on this RFID in order to increase its reliability and effectiveness. An indicator or an LCD screen can be incorporated into the system to indicate when any unregistered card is scanned. An IP camera can be integrated into this system to monitor the actions like buddy-punching wherein a person cheats by scanning for another person. Finally, this attendance system can be improved by adding a feature where the attendance system indicates when a student is late for work or classes as the case maybe [15].

X. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the automatic student's attendance using RFID. RFID has many applications as can be imagine. Finally, based on the application scenario proposed we develop a monitoring system and discussed the flow of the overall system. The application will improve management procedure. It is mainly used to avoid the proxy attendance. The use of RFID in implementing functional and automatic student attendance recording system fill their attendance just by swiping or moving their ID cards over the RFID readers which are located at the entrance of class or lecture hall. This paper works not only for the ideal case consisting of fixed number of students with fixed

number of classes it can also works with variable number of students in variable number of classes. With only limited and minimum number of modules it is easy to fix and use. The system checks the absentees and sends the message to the parents, class admin using the GSM modem. The parents are alerted that their son/daughter is absent for the selected class and the class admin will mark the absentees on the attendance sheet.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dawes A.T. (2004), "Is RFID Right for Your Library", *Journal of Access Services*, Volume 2(4), pp 7-13.
- [2] Zatin Singhal and Rajneesh Kumar Gujral. "Anytime anywhere- Remote Monitoring of Attendance System based on RFID using GSM Network". in *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975–8887). 2012; 39(3)
- [3] Gao, J. Z., Prakash, L., & Jagatesan, R. (2007). Understanding 2D-BarCode Technology and Applications in M-Commerce- Design and Implementation of a 2D Barcode Processing Solution. 31st Annual International Computer Software and Application.
- [4] Elisabeth Ilie-Zudor, Zsolt Kemeny, Peter Egri, Laszlo Monostori. "The RFID Technology and its Current Applications" in *MITIP-2006*.
- [5] US. Government Accountability Office, "Information Security: Radio Frequency Identification Technology in the Federal Government", (2005), Report to Congressional Requesters, GAO-05-551.
- [6] Kato, H., & Tan, K. T. (2005). 2D Barcode for Mobile Phone. Second International Conference on Mobile Technology, Application and System, 15-17 November 2005 Japanons Conference 23-27 July 2007 Beijing.
- [7] J. Schwieren1, G. Vossen, "A Design and Development Methodology for Mobile RFID Applications based on the ID-Services Middleware Architecture", IEEE Computer Society, (2009), Tenth International
- [8] Joseph, D. I., & Nakhoda, Y. I. (2008). Students Attendance by Using RFID Informed Through SMS. Fourth International Conference on Information and Communication Technology and System, 5 August 2008.
- [9] Stockman, H. (1948). Communication by Means of Reflected Power Proceedings of the Institute of Radio Engineers. October. pp 1196-1204.
- [10] J.Schwieren1, G.Vossen, "A Design and Development Methodology for Mobile RFID Applications based on the ID-Services Middleware Architecture", IEEE Computer Society, (2009), Tenth International Conference on Mobile Data Management: Systems, Service and Middleware.
- [11] R. Want, "Enabling Ubiquitous Sensing with RFID," *Computer*, vol.37, no. 4, 2004, pp. 84–86.
- [12] Manelis V.B, Kaioukov I.V, and Novikov A.V, (2009) "Identification and Analysis of Interference Effects of GSM Base Stations", *CJSC IRKOS, Radio electronics and Communications Systems*, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 55-62.
- [13] Albrecht, K., and McIntyre, L. (2005). *Spychips : How Major Corporations and Government Plan to Track Your Every Move with RFID*. Nelson Current Publishing.
- [14] Longe O.O., "Implementation of Student Attendance System using RFID Technology", B. Tech Project Report, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, Nigeria, (2008).
- [15] Shashank Shukla, "RFID Based Attendance Management System", *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)* Vol. 3, No. 6, December 2013, pp. 784~790.